

Low Power High Speed Adder's using GDI Logic

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Abstract

Multiplication, subtraction, and division all stem from addition, making it an essential mathematical operation. To add two binary integers, one needs an adder, a digital circuit. An arithmetic unit's fundamental building component is the 1-bit full adder. Digital circuit design is greatly simplified with very large scale integration (VLSI). A few examples of these methods include CMOS, Transmitter gate, and Pass Transistor logic (PTL). In order to lower the power consumption, several adder designs have been used. The problem is that every single design has its own unique drawback. There are two types of adder designs: one with strong driving capabilities and one with greater delay, the latter of which uses less power. Using Gate Diffusion Input (GDI) logic, this work implements many 8-bit Carry Increment Adders (CIAs), Carry Bypass Adders (CBAs), Carry Skip Adders (CSKAs), and Carry Look Ahead Adders (CLAs). The Tanner tool is used to simulate and execute these designs. According to the results, when comparing GDI logic designs to CMOS logic, CBA, CLA, and CSKA are more efficient in terms of power consumption, latency, and area (transistors count), respectively.

Keywords: Electricity use, GDI, CMOS, Adder

Introduction

The basic building blocks of arithmetic operations in very large scale integration are adders. Floating point units, ALUs, and CPUs often use adders. A basic adder is

either a half or a full adder. One essential feature of CMOS logic, which is often used to create these circuits, is its great noise tolerance. Power consumption rises as circuit speed and complexity increase. The need for portable electronics like smartphones and laptops is on the rise, necessitating circuit designs that are economical with both space and power while yet providing fast processing speeds, solid dependability, compact dimensions, and extended battery life. Both high-performance and portable systems are governed by power and area.

1. Review of Written Works
Low power applications saw the replacement of CMOS logic with Gate Diffusion Input (GDI) logic. This GDI logic simplifies digital circuits by cutting down on latency, area, and power consumption. PMOS transistors in complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) circuits are designed to only accept input voltage or another PMOS transistor. The same holds true for NMOS transistors; they need either a ground input or an NMOS transistor. The three inputs that make up GDI logic are G, P, and N. Several logic tools that use GDI logic (which only requires two transistors) are shown in table 1.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of GDI Logic

N	P	G	Out	Function
'0'	B	A	$\overline{A}B$	F1
B	'1'	A	$\overline{A} + B$	F2
'1'	B	A	$A + B$	OR
B	'0'	A	AB	AND
C	B	A	$\overline{A}B + AC$	MUX
'0'	'1'	A	$\overline{A}$	NOT

Table 1. Several logic utilities of GDI Logic Configurations for Input

1. Proposed Work

Carry Increment Adder

The block diagram of CIA is shown in figure 2. The 8-bit CIA contains two 4-bit Ripple Carry Adders (RCA). The 1st RCA adds a required number of 1st 4-bit inputs producing sum and carry. Now the carry out of the 1st RCA is applied to Cin of the conditional increment block. Thus the 1st 4-bit sum is straightly taken from the ripple carry output. The 2nd RCA makes the addition operation irrespective of the 1st RCA output and will give out results which are fed to the conditional increment block. The input Cin to the 1st RCA is at all times low value. The conditional increment block comprises of half adders. Based on the value of Cout of the 1st RCA, the increment operation will take place. The increment process

carried by the half adder in carry increment block. The 2nd RCA output i.e. sum is taken through the carry increment block.

Figure 2. Block Diagram of CIA

Carry Increment Adder

The block diagram of CBA is shown in figure 3. In RCA, each full adder waits for the incoming carry to generate an outgoing carry. This need can be removed by presenting an extra bypass to speed up the action of the adder. An incoming carry $C_{i,0}=1$ transmits through whole adder chain and causes an outgoing carry $C_{0,7}=1$ below the conditions that

all transmission signals are 1. The operation of the adder can be speed up using this data. When $P_0P_1P_2P_3P_4P_5P_6P_7 = 1$, the incoming carry is sent to the next block through the bypass and if it is not the case, the carry is obtained via the normal route. If $(P_0P_1P_2P_3P_4P_5P_6P_7 = 1)$ then $C_{0,7} = C_{i,0}$ else either generate or delete happened. In CBA, full adders are separated into groups, each of them is “bypassed” by a mux, when all the full adders are in propagating.

Figure 3. Block Diagram of CBA

Carry Skip Adder

The block diagram of CSA is shown in figure 4. A CSKA consists of a RCA with a skip chain used to speed up the carry chain. This chain explains the sharing of ripple carry blocks, which comprise the skip adder. The worst case for a RCA occurs,

when the transmit state is true for each pair (a_i, b_i) . For each operand input bit pair (a_i, b_i) the transmit conditions are determined using an XOR gate. When all transmit conditions are true, then the carry-in bit determines the carry-out bit. The n-bit CSKA consists of mux, AND gate with n-inputs and n-bit carry ripple chain. The carry ripple chain provides transmit bit, which is connected to the AND gate. The mux uses the resultant bit as a select bit that changes either the carry-in to the carry-out

signal or last carry bit.

Figure 4. Block Diagram of CSKA Carry Look Ahead Adder

The figure 5 shows the block diagram of CLA. The CLA computes carry bits before the sum, which decreases the wait time to compute the result of the higher bit value. In CLA to make addition much faster, propagate and generate logics are able to generate

carries before the sum is produced. Full adder circuit develops two logics carry Generate ($G_i = A_i \text{ AND } B_i$), and carry propagate ($P_i = A_i \text{ XOR } B_i$). The output can be conveyed as sum ($S_i = P_i \text{ XOR } C_i$) and carry ($C_{i+1} = G_i + P_i C_i$). G_i =carry generate and P_i =carry propagate, because it is term associated with the propagation of the carry from C_i to C_{i+1} . The carry output of each stage is $C_2 = G_1 + P_1 C_1$, $C_3 = G_2 + P_2 C_2 = G_2 + P_2 (G_1 + P_1 C_1) = G_2 + P_2 G_1 + P_2 P_1 C_1$, $C_4 = G_3 + P_3 C_3$. C_4 , C_3 and C_2 are transmitted at the same time. Each output carry are expressed in sum of product form.

Figure 5. Block Diagram of CLA

Figure 6. 8-bit CIA Adder Design

2. Results

The schematic diagrams of AND, NOR, OR, and EXOR gates, basic modules of half adder and full adder, 8-bit CIA, CBA, CSKA, and CLA are shown in figures 6 to 13 respectively using Tanner. In the architecture of CMOS adders, the CMOS basic modules like AND, NOR, OR, and EXOR gates, half and full adders are used. The architecture of GDI adders is same as CMOS adders but CMOS basic modules are replaced with GDI basic modules.

Figure 7. Output waveforms for 8-Bit CIA for Adding of $(1101\ 1011)_2$ and $(1110\ 1110)_2$

Figure 8. CBA Adder Design

Figure 9. Output waveforms for 8-Bit CBA for adding of $(0101\ 1101)_2$ and $(1011\ 1101)_2$

Figure 10. 8-bit CSKA adder Gate Design

Figure 11. Output waveforms for 8-Bit CSKA for Adding of $(1111\ 0111)_2$ and $(1100\ 1111)_2$

Figure 12. 8-bit CLA Adder Design

Figure 13. Output waveforms for 8-Bit CLA for Adding of $(1100\ 1111)_2$ and $(1111\ 1101)_2$

References

- [1] S Bharathi “Area Efficient Self Timed Adders for Low Power Applications in VLSI”, I. J. of innovative Research in Science, Engg and Technology, Vol. 4, Issue 2, Feb 2015.
- [2] Jashanpreet kaur, et.al. “A Review on GDI”, I. J of Advance Research in Electronics, Electrical & Computer Science Applications of Engg & Technology, Vol. 2, Issue 4, July 2014.
- [3] P.Chaitanya Kumari, “Design of 32 bit Parallel Prefix Adders”, IOSR Journal of Electronics and Communication Engg, Vol.6, Issue 1, May 2013.
- [4] Adilakshmi siliveru, “Design of KSA and BKA using Degenerate PTL”, I.J. of Emerging Science and Engg, Vol. 1(4), 2013, pp.2319–6378.
- [5] Arun Prakash Singh, “Implementation of 1-Bit Full Adder using GDI Cell”, I.J.of Electronics and Computer Science Engineering, Vol.1, Issue 2, pp.333-342, 2012.
- [6] Madhu Thakur, “ Design of Braun Multiplier with KS A & its Implementation on FPGA”, I.J. of Scientific & Engg Research, Vol.3, Issue 10, Oct-2012.
- [7] S. Veeramachaneni, “Efficient Design of 32-Bit Comparator using CLA Logic,” in Proceedings of the IEEE NEWCAS '07, August 2007, pp.867–870.